

ICP analysis

Deliverable 3.3, SOPs for all Physicochemical Methods, Annex I

SOP for ICP analysis

GRACIOUS digestion protocols for composition and impurity analysis – Hotplate digestion and ICP analysis

General considerations

Weighing: analytical balance, with frequent use of a static gun (Merck, Zerostat) to remove static build up on samples and Teflon beakers. Samples were not dried before digestion.

Digestions were carried out in 100 ml Teflon beakers (pre acid cleaned) on a Teflon heating block using gentle reflux. As required, heating was maintained until complete dissolution of the solid was achieved (by visual confirmation). Note for CeO₂ NFs this was achieved with varying success between laboratories.

ICPMS measurement: Perkin Elmer NeXION 300D

- **Modality of the collision/reaction cell used:** standard mode without KED or DRC
- **Reaction mode was not used.**
- **Nebulising gas flow:** Instrument was optimised for oxides (CeO/Ce) < 0.03. Nebulising gas flow usually optimised between 0.94 and 0.99 litres/min
- **Blanks:** Duplicate blanks were run for each digestion procedure.

ICPOES measurement, Fe: Perkin Elmer Optima 7500 DV

Fe, 239.6 nm radial view mode, Calibration range 0-1000 mg/l

All digest solutions were diluted before ICP measurement, see individual material sections for details.

6 Impurities measured within the GRACIOUS project are:

- Cr, mass 52, Sc(45), 0-10 µg/l
- Mg, mass 24, Sc(45), 0-100 µg/l
- Mn, mass 55, Sc(45), 0-100 µg/l
- Ni, mass 60, Sc(45), 0-10 µg/l
- Pb, mass 208, Re(185), 0-100 µg/l
- Sr, mass 88, Rh(103), 0-100 µg/l

Summary of all analytes in GRACIOUS:

Ag, mass 107/109, internal standard In(115), calibration range 0-10 µg/l

Mg, mass 24, Sc(45), 0-100 µg/l

Cr, mass 52, Sc(45), 0-10 µg/l

Mn, mass 55, Sc(45), 0-100 µg/l

Ni, mass 60, Sc(45), 0-10 µg/l

Zn, mass 66, Sc(45), 0-100 µg/l

Cu, mass 65, Sc(45), 0-100 µg/l

Se, mass 82, Rh(103), 0-100 µg/l

Sr, mass 88, Rh(103), 0-100 µg/l

Cd, mass 114, Rh(103), 0-100 µg/l

In, mass 115, Rh(103), 0-100 µg/l

Ba, mass 137, Tb(159), 0-100 µg/l

Ce, mass 140, Tb(159), 0-100 µg/l

Pb, mass 208, Re(185), 0-100 µg/l

Reagents

- Ultra-pure water: Millipore synergy >18 Ω Ohm (UPW) was used throughout.
- Tween 20: Sigma-aldrich
- Concentrated nitric acid: Baker Ultrex II, 70%
- Nitric acid 0.1 M: dilute concentrated HNO₃ as required
- Hydrogen peroxide 30%: Supelco, for trace analysis
- Sulphuric acid >95%: s.g. 1.83, 'Aristar' grade

Material specifics:

Cerium Oxide

Weight taken: ~ 0.05 g

Reagent: 1 ml H₂O₂ and 4 ml HNO₃

Preparation: pre-digested in H₂O₂ overnight at room temperature, then HNO₃ added and sample digested with gentle heating

Final volume: 25 ml achieved by the addition of 20 ml UPW to the digested sample

Zinc Oxide

Weight taken: ~ 0.05 g

Reagent: Aqua regia, 6 ml of a 1:3 mixture of HNO₃/HCl, 'Aristar' grade

Preparation: gentle heating

Final volume: 25 ml

Silver nanomaterials

Weight taken: approx. 0.05 g

Reagent: 2 ml HNO₃

Preparation: room temperature

Final volume: 25 ml

CuPhthalo_nano

Weight taken: ~ 0.005 g

Reagent: Tween 20, 1% v/v in UPW

Preparation: material was dispersed using bath sonication

Final volume: 25 ml

Iron oxide

Weight taken: ~ 0.05 g

Reagent: Aqua regia, 6 ml of a 1:3 mixture of HNO₃/HCl, 'Aristar' grade

Preparation: gentle heating

Final volume: 25 ml

Barium sulphate

Weight taken: ~ 0.005 g

Reagent: 2 ml H₂SO₄ (95%)

Preparation: gentle heating

Final volume: 25 ml

Quantum dots

Weight taken: ~ 0.01 g

Reagent: 0.1M and concentrated HNO₃.

ZnCdSeS, ZnCdSeS-COOH: 10 ml 0.1M followed by 2 ml concentrated HNO₃

ZnCuInS/ZnS: 7 ml 0.1M HNO₃

ZnCuInS/ZnS_smaller, ZnCuInS/ZnS_larger: 5 ml 0.1M HNO₃

Final volume: 25 ml